

Supplementary information for

DNA metabarcoding reveals unexpected predator-prey-microbial dynamics in a Southern Ocean predator (*Eubalaena australis*)

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Table S1. PCR conditions for the three metabarcoding primers used in this study. PCRs were performed in two rounds with conditions for the second round being the same for all three primer sets.

PCR Round 1						
Amplicon	PCR Mixture		PCR Conditions			
	Reagent	Volume (uL)	PCR Stage	Temperature	Time	PCR cycles
18S	Mastermix	10	Initial denaturation	95°C	8 min	x 35
	Primer-F (0.5uM)	3.5	Denaturation	95°C	20 s	
	Primer-R (0.5uM)	3.5	Annealing	58°C	20 s	
	PNA clamp*	1	Elongation	72°C	30 s	
	DNA	2	Final elongation	72°C	8 min	
Crust16S	Mastermix	10	Initial denaturation	95°C	10 min	x 45
	Primer-F (0.5uM)	4	Denaturation	95°C	20 s	
	Primer-R (0.5uM)	4	Annealing	51°C	30 s	
	DNA	2	Elongation	72°C	45 s	
			Final elongation	72°C	10 min	
16S	Mastermix	10	Initial denaturation	95°C	10 min	x 30
	Primer-F (0.5uM)	4	Denaturation	95°C	20 s	
	Primer-R (0.5uM)	4	Annealing	50°C	30 s	
	DNA	2	Elongation	72°C	45 s	
			Final elongation	72°C	5 min	
PCR Round 2						
<p>The second round of PCR for all 3 amplicons added Illumina Unique Dual Indexes (UDIs) from index adapter sets A, B and C. Each PCR reaction was 16 mL, including Q5 High-Fidelity 2X Master Mix (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA), 0.2 mM UDI, and 1 mL of product from the first round PCR diluted to 5%. The PCR conditions were: 30s of initial denaturation at 98°C; 14x PCR cycles of 10s denaturation at 98°C, 10s annealing at 57°C and 20s elongation at 72°C; concluding with a 1 min final elongation at 72°C.</p> <p>*Whale blocking PNA clamp: CGACCGTCTTCTCAGC-Lys</p>						

Table S2. Frequency of prey at finest taxonomic resolution detected at each calving/socialising ground (Algoa Bay, Auckland Islands and Fowlers Bay) and foraging ground (St Helena Bay).

Order	Species	Algoa Bay	Auckland Islands	Fowlers Bay	St Helena Bay
Polymorphida	Polymorphidae	0	2	0	0
Diplostraca	<i>Penilia avirostris</i>	1	1	4	10
Calanoida	Calanoida	0	0	1	9
	<i>Parvocalanus</i>				
Calanoida	<i>crassirostris</i>	1	0	0	0
Necopepoda	Necopepoda	1	0	1	10
Amphipoda	<i>Cyamus boopis</i>	0	0	0	4
Cumacea	<i>Diastylis laevis</i>	0	0	0	12
Decapoda	<i>Epilobocera capolongoi</i>	0	0	2	0
Decapoda	<i>Goneplax rhomboides</i>	0	0	0	1

Decapoda	<i>Hymenosoma geometricum</i>	0	0	0	1
Decapoda	<i>Hymenosoma orbiculare</i>	0	0	0	2
Decapoda	<i>Jasus</i>	0	0	0	1
Decapoda	<i>Monodaeus</i>	0	0	0	5
Decapoda	<i>Mursia cristiata</i>	0	0	0	4
Decapoda	<i>Neoxanthops quadrilobatus</i>	0	0	1	0
Decapoda	<i>Ovalipes trimaculatus</i>	0	0	0	4
Decapoda	Penaeoidea	0	0	0	1
Decapoda	<i>Pilumnoides perlatus</i>	0	0	2	11
Decapoda	<i>Pilumnus</i>	0	0	0	0
Decapoda	<i>Plagusia chabrus</i>	1	0	0	1
Decapoda	<i>Portunus</i>	1	0	2	4
Decapoda	<i>Thia scutellata</i>	0	1	1	5
Decapoda	Xanthidae	1	0	0	0
Euphausiacea	<i>Euphausia</i>	0	0	0	5
Euphausiacea	<i>Euphausia superba</i>	0	0	0	2
Euphausiacea	<i>Nyctiphanes australis</i>	1	1	2	0
Euphausiacea	<i>Thysanoessa gregaria</i>	0	0	1	2
Euphausiacea	<i>Thysanoessa</i> sp. BD-2006	0	0	0	3
Isopoda	<i>Scutuloidea maculata</i>	0	1	0	0
Stomatopoda	<i>Pterygosquilla schizodontia</i>	0	0	0	12
Aphragmophora	Sagittidae	0	0	0	2
Phlebobranchia	<i>Ciona intestinalis</i>	0	0	0	1
Leptothecata	Leptothecata	0	0	0	2
Scyphozoa	Scyphozoa	0	0	0	3
Semaeostomeae	<i>Chrysaora</i>	0	0	0	11
Semaeostomeae	Pelagiidae	0	0	0	2
Euheterodonta	Euheterodonta	0	0	1	0
Galeommatida	Montacutidae	1	0	1	0
Nudibranchia	<i>Jorunna tomentosa</i>	0	0	0	1
Plagiorchiida	Plagiorchiida	0	1	0	0

Table S3. Relative abundances of bacterial phyla detected in the gut microbiomes of SRWs from calving/socialising and foraging grounds.

Calving/socialising			Foraging		
Phylum	Mean relative abundance (%)	SE	Phylum	Mean relative abundance (%)	SE
<i>Firmicutes</i>	87.06	2.27	<i>Firmicutes</i>	76.22	3.20
<i>Actinobacteria</i>	8.38	1.09	<i>Bacteroidetes</i>	12.59	2.62
<i>Fusobacteria</i>	2.13	2.08	<i>Actinobacteria</i>	5.04	1.06
<i>Bacteroidetes</i>	1.33	0.92	<i>Spirochaetota</i>	3.58	1.36
<i>Proteobacteria</i>	0.48	0.33	<i>Proteobacteria</i>	1.05	0.26

<i>Verrucomicrobiota</i>	0.43	0.16	<i>Verrucomicrobiota</i>	1.02	0.26
<i>Synergistota</i>	0.09	0.05	<i>Euryarchaeota</i>	0.19	0.06
<i>Spirochaetota</i>	0.04	0.02	<i>Mycoplasmata</i>	0.10	0.04
<i>Euryarchaeota</i>	0.04	0.03	<i>Synergistota</i>	0.10	0.03
<i>Lentisphaerota</i>	0.02	0.01	<i>Lentisphaerota</i>	0.09	0.04
<i>Mycoplasmata</i>	0.001	0.001	<i>Fusobacteria</i>	0.01	0.01
<i>Cyanobacteriota</i>	0.000	0.000	<i>Cyanobacteriota</i>	0.004	0.002
<i>Planctomycetota</i>	0.000	0.000	<i>Planctomycetota</i>	0.003	0.002

Table S4. Relative abundances of top 10 most abundant bacterial classes (or higher taxonomic levels not resolved to the genus) detected in the gut microbiomes of SRWs from calving/socialising and foraging grounds each.

Calving/socialising			Foraging		
Order	Mean relative abundance (%)	SE	Order	Mean relative abundance (%)	SE
<i>Clostridia</i>	63.82	4.01	<i>Clostridia</i>	66.68	3.79
<i>Erysipelotrichia</i>	17.61	4.68	<i>Bacteroidia</i>	12.53	2.62
<i>Coriobacteriia</i>	7.48	1.03	<i>Erysipelotrichia</i>	6.52	2.20
<i>Firmicutes_c</i>	3.00	1.13	<i>Coriobacteriia</i>	3.78	0.77
<i>Bacilli</i>	2.49	2.31	<i>Spirochaetia</i>	3.58	1.36
<i>Fusobacteriia</i>	2.13	2.08	<i>Firmicutes_c</i>	1.92	0.63
<i>Bacteroidia</i>	1.31	0.91	<i>Actinobacteria_c</i>	1.25	0.65
<i>Actinobacteria_c</i>	0.90	0.12	<i>Bacilli</i>	0.63	0.30
<i>Gammaproteobacteria</i>	0.43	0.31	<i>Verrucomicrobiota</i>	0.60	0.20
<i>Verrucomicrobiota_c</i>	0.29	0.13	<i>Betaproteobacteria</i>	0.49	0.18

Table S5. Relative abundances of top 25 most abundant bacterial genera (or higher taxonomic levels not resolved to the genus) detected in the gut microbiomes of SRWs from calving/socialising and foraging grounds each.

Calving/socialising			Foraging		
Genus	Mean relative abundance (%)	SE	Genus	Mean relative abundance (%)	SE
<i>Romboutsia</i>	23.69	5.45	<i>Clostridium sensu stricto</i>	28.68	6.34
<i>Faecalibaculum</i>	16.12	4.79	<i>Phocaeicola</i>	7.68	1.72
<i>Clostridium sensu stricto</i>	8.02	3.47	<i>Oscillospiraceae_g</i>	7.65	1.31
<i>Coriobacteriia_g</i>	5.23	0.80	<i>Romboutsia</i>	4.61	1.77
<i>Ihubacter</i>	4.47	0.69	<i>Vescimonas</i>	3.63	0.92
<i>Oscillospiraceae_g</i>	4.23	0.91	<i>Treponema</i>	3.55	1.35
<i>Peptococcus</i>	3.96	1.02	<i>Terrisporobacter</i>	3.48	1.36
<i>Firmicutes_g</i>	3.00	1.13	<i>Faecalibaculum</i>	2.80	1.68
<i>Mediterraneibacter</i>	2.71	0.77	<i>Faecalitalea</i>	2.75	1.58

<i>Guopingia</i>	2.51	1.47	<i>Flintibacter</i>	2.60	1.28
<i>Carnobacterium</i>	2.30	2.15	<i>Lachnospiraceae_g</i>	2.46	0.81
<i>Cetobacterium</i>	2.13	2.08	<i>Prevotellamassilia</i>	2.16	0.63
<i>Mogibacterium</i>	2.12	0.46	<i>Firmicutes_g</i>	1.92	0.63
<i>Peptacetobacter</i>	1.95	0.76	<i>Ihubacter</i>	1.78	0.58
<i>Gallibacter</i>	1.66	0.86	<i>Coriobacteriia_g</i>	1.58	0.56
<i>Dorea</i>	1.21	0.37	<i>Peptococcus</i>	1.58	0.35
<i>Eubacteriaceae_g</i>	1.17	0.14	<i>Guopingia</i>	1.49	0.88
<i>Lachnospiraceae_g</i>	1.03	0.47	<i>Xylanibacter</i>	1.22	0.37
<i>Eubacteriales_g</i>	0.94	0.21	<i>Curtanaerobium</i>	1.08	0.40
<i>Erysipelotrichaceae_g</i>	0.88	0.15	<i>Bariatricus</i>	0.99	0.43
<i>Atopobiaceae_g</i>	0.81	0.40	<i>Eubacteriales_g</i>	0.93	0.19
<i>Oscillibacter</i>	0.81	0.28	<i>Bifidobacterium</i>	0.89	0.62
<i>Lentihominibacter</i>	0.61	0.15	<i>Oscillibacter</i>	0.88	0.18
<i>Vescimonas</i>	0.55	0.13	<i>Mediterraneibacter</i>	0.85	0.46
<i>Curtanaerobium</i>	0.50	0.15	<i>Dorea</i>	0.70	0.21

Fig. S1. Proportion of gut bacterial classes (or higher taxonomic levels not resolved to class) with >5% total relative abundance, detected in whale faecal samples from calving/socialising and foraging grounds. Only

samples where prey was also detected have been included (59% of the whales from calving/socialising grounds and 86% of the whales from the foraging grounds).

Fig. S2. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of Hellinger transformed (a) SRW prey communities and (b) gut bacterial communities, with prey communities grouped by SRW migratory stages: calving/socialising and foraging

Fig. S3. Tanglegram comparing the clustering of gut bacterial and prey communities in the sampled SRWs. The straight bars connecting the prey and bacterial communities suggest high similarity in community

structure, with significant clusters highlighted in dark pink. Sample names are coloured in light purple for calving/socialising SRWs and dark purple for foraging SRWs.

Table S6. ANOVA results for stepwise selection model used to select SRW prey groups significantly associated with gut bacterial communities.

	Df	Variance	F	Pr(>F)	
Cumacea	1	0.01556	1.2212	0.203	
Decapoda	1	0.01693	1.329	0.19	
Euphausiacea	1	0.02977	2.3364	0.025	*
Neocopepoda	1	0.03685	2.8919	0.009	**
Polymorphida	1	0.02604	2.0437	0.022	*
Semaeostomeae	1	0.07392	5.8009	0.001	***
Stomatopoda	1	0.03317	2.6027	0.001	***